

Selected Delphi panel

FROM 6 EU COUNTRIES

DK

Researchers:6

Policy makers:6

National level:2
Regional level:1
Local level:3

FIN

Researchers:6

Policy makers:6

National level:5
Regional level:1
Local level:-

IT

Researchers:6

Policy makers:6

National level:1
Regional level:1
Local level:4

NL

Researchers:7

Policy makers:5

National level:2
Regional level:-
Local level:3

RO

Researchers:6

Policy makers:6

National level:4
Regional level:2
Local level: -

UK

Researchers:6

Policy makers:6

National level:5
Regional level:1
Local level:-

FROM INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

INT

Researchers:4

Policy makers:6

International level